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A Preliminary Evaluation of *Panicum sarmentosum*, A Local Grass Species Potentially Used as a Trap Crop for Controlling Fall Armyworm

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Abstract

Currently, the invasive pest *Spodoptera frugiperda* poses a significant risk to maize crops, as it has the potential to lead to complete yield loss if not properly controlled. This study aimed to explore the potency of *Panicum sarmentosum*, a local grass in Central Sulawesi, Indonesia, as a trap crop to combat this voracious pest. The feeding preference test (two-choice and no-choice test) was conducted in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) consisting of five forage grasses, i.e. *P. sarmentosum*, *Brachiaria mulato*, Pakchong, *Pennisetum purpureum*, and *Zea mays* as a control for comparison of their potential as trap crops. The leaf area consumed by *S. frugiperda* and the growth of *S. frugiperda* fed on grass leaves were measured to evaluate their suitability as the host plants. The results revealed that although maize leaf was the most preferred by FAW larvae to consume, the sarmentose panicum leaves were also chosen by this pest. *P. sarmentosum* leaf, was the third-ranked choice after maize and Pakchong leaves in the two-choice tests, while in the no-choice test, it was the second preference. The FAW larvae feeding on *P. sarmentosum* grow and develop surpass than those on mulato grass, supporting that this local grass is suitable as feed and supports the growth of FAW. These results indicated that *P. sarmentosum* might be used as a trap crop against FAW as one sustainable control method for this maize pest, although further tests are still needed.

Keywords: Fall armyworm, feeding preferences, trap crops, local grass, *P. sarmentosum*

INTRODUCTION

Fall armyworm (FAW), *Spodoptera frugiperda* (JE Smith) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae), is an economically important pest of maize, *Zea mays* L. (Poaceae), and has more than 350 host plant species belonging to the Poaceae, Asteraceae, and Fabaceae crops (Montezano et al., 2018). Its rapid proliferation has led to severe agricultural damage, particularly in maize production. In Africa, losses due to FAW were estimated between 8.3 - 20.6 million tons annually, valued at \$2.481-6.187 million USD/year (Ginting et al., 2021). In Indonesia, the severity of FAW Infestation on maize fields varied. It has been reaching burdensome levels in the Bali islands (Supartha et al., 2021) while in Central Java, it can cause serious damage, leading to almost total yield loss (Trisyono et al., 2024). In North Sumatra, the pest caused a 26.6% reduction in maize production and increased production costs by 4.2% (Girsang et al., 2020). A recent survey reported that the FAW infestation in Indonesia continues to increase, reaching 12,866.33 ha in the 2024/2025 planting season (Ashar & Prasetyaningtiyas, 2025).

Farmers have primarily relied on chemical pesticides for control of the FAW, although some have adopted cultural, mechanical and biological methods (Togola et al., 2025). An increasing pesticide contamination in agroecosystems causes adverse effects on the environment, including natural enemies, and other non-target organisms (Dhuldhaj et al., 2023). Moreover, FAW has been detected as among of the 15 most resistant species to some types of insecticides (Kulye et al., 2021). Therefore, the need in developing a sustainable management is critical for effective FAW control including implementing the trap cropping system such us trap cropping system.

Trap crops are utilized to lure pests away from cash crops, thereby safeguarding them against pest attacks. The trap crop can be either from the same family as the primary crop or from a different one, and it can be applied in different methods, such as the “Push–Pull” cropping technique (Shelton & Badenes-Perez, 2006). This technique involves planting pest-repellent ("push") plant species alongside a pest-attractive trap ("pull") plant species along the borders. For instance, various forage grasses like *Brachiaria* sp., *Panicum maximum*, and napier grass (*Pennisetum purpureum*) have been employed in the push-pull strategy, showing an 86% reduction in fall armyworm infestations and crop losses, which significantly boosted corn grain yields by up to 2.7 (Cheruiyot et al., 2021; Guera et al., 2020; Kumar et al., 2022; Midega et al., 2018; Tsai et al., 2024).

The effectiveness of trap crops in suppressing pest populations mainly hinges on their inherent characteristics and the strategic deployment in the fields. For instance, the FAW feeding preference and its growth rate are affected by the nutritional content and also the phenolic acid of the plant consumed (Ajmal et al., 2024; Dowd et al., 2018). Meanwhile, various combinations of the push-pull crops resulted in different results in managing the FAW (Guera et al., 2021; Sileshi et al., 2025). Accordingly, selecting the potential trap crop at the laboratory or greenhouse is a crucial step before implementing this pest management strategy.

In attempting to search and select a potential trap plant for FAW management, this study is designed to test the prospect of the local grass Sarmentose Panicum (*Panicum sarmentosum* Roxb) for use as a trap crop against FAW. This grass was first recorded growing in the Palu valley, Central Sulawesi, Indonesia in 1999, and spread to various types of habitats at altitudes 0 -700 m asl. This grass has a high potential as forage for the ruminantia due to its nutritional values (Amar et al., 2020; Tarsono et al., 2022). The specific question addressed by this study is: 1) Do the FAW prefer *P. sarmentosum* or other grasses as their feed?, 2) In which grass can the FAW larvae grow better, and is it correlated with their chemical substances of the grass?

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In addition to *P. sarmentosum*, this study also employs three introduced forage grasses as comparative species. The comparative grasses are: mulato (*Brachiaria mulato*); pakchong, which is a hybrid of elephant grass (*Pennisetum purpureum*) with pearl millet (*Pennisetum americanum*), was developed in Pakchong Thailand; and elephant grass (*Pennisetum purpureum*). These three species have been used as trap crops in pactices and in many studies (Cheruiyot et al., 2021; Guera et al., 2021; Kumar et al., 2022; Tsai et al., 2024). *P. sarmentoseum* were taken from the intensive feed garden of the Faculty of Animal Husbandry and Fishery, University of Tadulako, while the rest grasses and *Zea mays* (Pertiwi 1) were bought from a seedling distributor. All plants were growing in a greenhouse before being used in the laboratory experiment. The Larvae of *S. frugiperda* were mass-reared at the laboratory of Plant Pest Diseases of Tadulako University following the method described in (Wangi et al., 2022) for use in laboratory experiments. The insect rearing room temperature and humidity were 28°C and 51 %, respectively. The room temperature is within the optimal range for the development of FAW from egg to imago stage (Plessis et al., 2020).

Feeding preference of *S. frugiperda*

The feeding preference test of *S. frugiperda* larvae refers to (Guera et al., 2020) using a two-choice and a no-choice test. In the two-choice test, the following treatments were used: maize vs. Pakchong, maize vs. *P. purpureum*, maize vs. *P. sarmentosum*, and maize vs. *B. mulato*. A fresh leaves pieces (3 cm x 2 cm) of each host plant (40 days-old seedlings) were placed in a petri dish (9 cm diameter x 1.5 cm height) and lined

with filter paper and small wet cotton balls on the edge of the petri dish. One third-instar of *S. frugiperda* larvae was placed in the center of each petri dish equidistant from the both leaves tested. In the no-choice test, the leaf pieces of each plant were placed in separate petri dishes then FAW larvae were released into the petri dishes. In both tests, FAW larvae were fasted for 3 hours before feeding, and the percentage of leaf area eaten was recorded after 10 hours of exposure to FAW larvae. The leaf area consumed was measured using the BioLeaf application (Machado et al., 2016). The experiment was carried out in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD), which was replicated 12 times for each treatment.

Development and body size of *S. frugiperda* larvae

The effect of forage grass species consumed on the development of *S. frugiperda* larvae was observed by exposing the larvae to a 3 cm x 2 cm fresh leaf collected from well-developed leaves of each grass species. The leaves were replaced with fresh ones daily until the larvae developed into pupae. The development time from the third instar, pupae, and the imago was observed daily. The size of the pupae was measured using a digital vernier caliper.

Phenolic contents of leaves

The leaves of each grass (40 days-old seedlings) were collected to analyze their phenolic content in the Chemical laboratory of the Faculty of Mathematics and Sciences, University of Tadulako. The total phenolic content of the grass leaves was determined with Folin-Ciocalteu reagent and using gallic acid as a standard phenolic compound as described by (Orak, 1998) to evaluate its possible correlation on feeding preferences and development of FAW larvae.

Data analysis

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) and multiple comparisons among the treatments (DMRT test) were performed to analyze the significant effects of the treatment by using the Statistix 8 software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RESULTS

Feeding preference of *S. frugiperda*

Based on the choice test, *S. frugiperda* larvae prefer to consume corn leaves compared to other leaves. The leaf area consumed by them is around 26.8 – 36.8%. However, other leaves were also chosen to be eaten, with the order of highest preference being Pakchong (7.5%), *P. sarmentosum* (5.4%), *B. mulato* (2.7%), and *P. purpureum* (2.4%) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Comparison of the of leaf area eaten by *S. frugiperda* larvae using a choice test

The no-choice test showed similar results, where *S. frugiperda* larvae consumed less of the grass leaves served than corn leaves. The highest leaf area consumed by *S. frugiperda* larvae was corn (64.0%), followed

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by *P. sarmentosum* (40.9%), Pakchong (35.6%), *P. purpureum* (35.2%), and *B. mulato* (21.46%) (Figure 2). Leaf area of corn leave consumed by FAW larvae was significantly higher than all other grass leaves while *P. sarmentosum*, Pakchong, and *P. purpureum* was statistically similar and the less feed consumed by FAW larvae was Pakchong.

Figure 2. Percentage of leaf area consumed by *S. frugiperda* larvae in the different treatments. Different letters indicate a significant difference by DMRT test ($P < 0.01$).

Development and body size of *S. frugiperda* larvae

The developmental time from the third larval to pupal stages, as well as the duration of the pupal and imago stages, varied among the grasses consumed. The shortest instar and pupal developmental time was found in *S. frugiperda* larvae fed maize leaves, while the longest was found in *B. mulato*. The longest duration of imago was observed in larvae fed on *B. mulato*, but this was not significantly different from that of larvae fed on maize. Meanwhile, the shortest duration was for those fed on *B. mulato* leaves. The size of pupae differed among grasses. The largest pupal size was those fed on maize leaves, followed by Pakchong, *P. sarmentosum*, and *B. mulato*, respectively (Table 1).

Table 1. Development time and the size of FAW (n=12) feeding on different grass species

Grass species	Duration (days)			Pupal size (mm)	
	The 3 rd instar to pupae	Pupae	Imago	Lenght	Diameter
<i>Zea mays</i>	21.08 ± 0.74 ^a	9.25 ± 0.17 ^a	8.25 ± 0.32 ^c	14.03 ± 0.38 ^c	3.24 ± 0.05 ^c
Pakchong	23.25 ± 0.42 ^b	9.50 ± 0.17 ^{ab}	8.50 ± 0.43 ^c	13.66 ± 0.10 ^{bc}	3.03 ± 0.05 ^b
<i>P. sarmentosum</i>	26.42 ± 0.74 ^c	10.00 ± 0.27 ^c	6.17 ± 1.81 ^{ab}	13.15 ± 0.39 ^a	2.96 ± 0.02 ^a
<i>P. purpureum</i>	24.50 ± 0.64 ^b	9.84 ± 0.33 ^{bc}	7.25 ± 1.10 ^{bc}	13.18 ± 0.25 ^a	2.95 ± 0.04 ^a
<i>B. mulato</i>	29.59 ± 1.93 ^d	10.67 ± 0.27 ^d	4.50 ± 1.81 ^a	13.48 ± 0.27 ^{ab}	2.90 ± 0.02 ^a

Means in the same row for each attribute with different superscripts are significantly different ($P < 0.01$).

Total phenolic content

The total phenol content of the five analyzed plant leaves varied. Corn leaves contained the lowest total phenol content compared to other forage grass, at 7.30 g, followed by Pakchong (25.90 g), *B. mulato* (35.10 g), *P. purpureum* (56.60 g), and *P. sarmentosum* (60.30 g) (Table 2).

Table 2. Total phenolic contents of different grass leaves

Grass species	Total Fenol (gGAE/g)
<i>Zea mays</i>	7.30
Pakchong	25.90
<i>P. sarmentosum</i>	60.30
<i>P. purpureum</i>	56.60
<i>B. mulato</i>	35.10

DISCUSSION

Various studies have revealed the potential of various forage grass species such as Pakchong,

Pennisetum purpureum, *Panicum maximum*, and *Brachiaria mulato* to be used as trap or repellent crops in a push-pull strategy for controlling *S. frugiperda* and other corn pests (Guera et al., 2020, 2021; Midega et al., 2018; Sileshi et al., 2025). The present study suggested that besides corn leaves, the primary host of *S. frugiperda*, *P. sarmentosum* leaves, were also preferred by FAW larvae. The percentage of *P. sarmentosum* leaf consumed by FAW larvae was 5.4% and 41.0% in the choice and no-choice tests, respectively, and it was higher than that of *P. purpureum* and *B. mulato* leaves and only slightly lower than that of Pakchong leaves.

Observations of FAW larval growth on various types of leaves also indicated that corn leaves are the most suitable for FAW larval development, with the shortest developmental duration and largest pupal size. The development of third-instar larvae to pupae and the pupal period only require 21 and 9.3 days, respectively. Meanwhile, the longest developmental durations of third-instar larvae and pupae were observed in larvae consuming mulato grass leaves, requiring 29.6 days and 10.67 days, respectively. This differs from that reported by (Subiono, 2020), where the development of third-instar FAW larvae on corn and mulato grass plants did not differ significantly, only around 21 days. Differences in results with this present study may occur because in this study, the FAW larvae were fed corn leaves, while that study provided corn plants as feed, which may affect the quality of the feed.

The best development of FAW larvae on corn leaves suggested that the chemical substances of this plant host better support their optimal growth than other grasses. Total phenolic levels in corn leaves are lower than in other leaves. Phenolic compounds are known to be secondary metabolites for plant defense that can interfere with insect growth, so in the field, they are often avoided by insects and prefer to attack host plants with lower phenol levels. For example, the growth rate of the FAW was correlated with the phenolic acid content of the plant consumed (Dowd et al., 2018), the differences in response and resistance of two maize varieties to FAW infestation due to their variation in phenolic and other chemical defense substances (Yang et al., 2023), and the lower population of the corn planthopper, *Stenocranus pacificus* was recorded at the maize variety containing less total phenolic (Saleh et al., 2024). On the other hand, *P. sarmentosum* leaves contain the highest phenolic content compared to other forage leaves. However, the developmental time of *S. frugiperda* pupae and adults fed on these leaves was similar to that of *P. purpureum* leaves but better than that of *B. mulato* leaves. This indicates that, in addition to phenol content, other factors, particularly the nutritional value of the feed, influence the growth and development of *S. frugiperda* larvae.

One of the most essential nutrients for insect growth is protein. Insect growth and development depend on proteins, which serve as building blocks for tissues, muscles, and organs. Proteins also play a role in several physiological processes, including the production of enzymes and hormones, and they play a role in the insect's immune system. For instance, changes in the total protein levels on the diet consumed can significantly affect the growth and performance of the phytophagous ladybug, *Henosepilachna vigintioctopunctata* (Wang et al., 2018), and differences in crude protein of plants selected positively correlated with growth rate and consumption rate of *S. frugiperda* larvae (Ajmal et al., 2024). The crude protein content of the *P. sarmentosum* is 9.77 % (Amar et al., 2020). This is almost similar to *Zea mays* leaves, which are about 9.30 – 9.93 % (Gökkuş et al., 2016). Contrastingly, crude proteins of Pakchong (15-19 %) and *B. mulato* (ca. 10 %) were higher than *Zea mays* and *P. sarmentosum* (Mohamad et al., 2022; Yiberkew et al., 2020), but their total phenol contents are between the latter two plants. Finally, the protein contents of *P. purpureum* varied from 3.7- 12.3 % depend on the harvesting time (Mendoza-Pedroza et al., 2022).

Some crops or plants are preferred by pests, while others are less favored. The ability of FAW to choose between different plants is affected by chemical signals (smell or taste) or physical signals (touch or sight) (Shelton & Badenes-Perez, 2006). Understanding which plants FAW prefer can help to create a non-chemical pest management strategy for this pest. These methods can be used to create trap crops and other agroecological pest control (Harrison et al., 2019). The present study revealed that *P. sarmentosum*, which naturally grows in the Palu valley, has the potential to be developed as a trap crop to control *S. frugiperda*. This is indicated by FAW larvae consuming more *P. sarmentosum* leaves and developing better than those fed on other forage grasses such as Napier grass or Mulato grass, which are widely used as trap crops in some countries (Cheruiyot et al., 2021; Khan et al., 2018; Midega et

al., 2018; Tsai et al., 2024).

P. sarmentosum has comparative advantages over other grasses for development as trap crops for *S. frugiperda*. This grass will provide two advantages if planted to surround the maize crops: it protects the maize from the FAW attack, and later on, the grass can be harvested and used as forage due to its good quality in terms of growth performance and nutritive value for the ruminants, as noted by (Amar et al., 2020; Tarsono; et al, 2009). However, further study is needed to be undertaken before implementing *P. sarmentosum* as a trap or pull crop for FAW. For example, we need to evaluate the oviposition preference of FAW for *sarmentosum* grass compared with other grasses in a screen house. Furthermore, its ability as a trap crop can be tested by intercropping the maize with *P. sarmentosum* surrounding or inside it. It is also possible to search the potency of *P. sarmentosum* to combine with the push crops such as desmodium (*Desmodium uncinatum* Jacq.) (Fabaceae) and molasses grass (*Melinis minutiflora* Beauv). Both push crops showed are reported suitable to integrate with the pull crops in managing maize pests (Khan et al., 2006, 2018; Sileshi et al., 2025).

CONCLUSIONS

Panicum sarmentosum potentially use as trap crops for controlling *S. frugiperda*. Although maize leaves were the most preferred by FAW larvae to consume, *P. sarmensum* leaves were also chosen by this pest. In the two-choice tests, *P. sarmentosum* was the third-ranked choice by FAW after maize and Pak Chong leaves, but in the no-choice test, it was the second preference. The FAW larvae feeding on *P. sarmentosum* larvae grow and develop better than on mulato grass, indicating that this local grass is quite suitable as feed and supports the growth of FAW.

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